

Study Outcome and Analysis Data

**Integrating Heritage Content
in Bahari Museum using
Design Game for Young Visitor
(Gen-Z)**

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User Data Result using UEQ Method

30 participants on 26 types of question varieties with 6 Element Aspect of UEQ

Items																										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	
6	6	2	2	2	6	7	4	2	2	6	1	6	7	7	7	2	2	2	6	2	6	2	1	2	6	
7	7	1	1	1	7	7	4	1	1	7	1	7	7	6	7	1	2	1	7	2	7	2	1	1	6	
7	7	1	1	1	7	7	7	1	1	6	2	6	7	6	6	1	2	1	6	1	6	1	2	2	6	
7	7	1	1	1	7	7	7	1	1	7	1	7	7	7	7	1	1	1	7	1	7	1	1	1	7	
4	2	2	4	6	6	4	4	4	2	6	4	4	4	6	4	4	2	4	4	2	6	2	4	1	2	
7	7	1	1	2	6	7	6	1	2	6	1	7	7	7	6	1	1	2	7	1	7	1	1	1	7	
4	7	6	2	4	2	2	7	4	6	2	4	6	2	6	4	2	4	4	2	2	2	6	4	2	4	
2	4	6	4	6	2	2	6	4	4	4	4	6	2	2	2	4	6	4	6	4	4	6	4	4	2	
6	7	4	1	4	6	7	4	6	4	7	4	7	7	4	4	1	4	2	7	6	2	6	1	2	6	
6	4	2	4	4	4	6	2	4	2	6	2	4	6	2	6	4	2	2	6	2	6	2	4	2	2	
7	7	2	1	2	6	7	7	1	1	7	2	6	4	7	7	1	1	1	7	1	7	2	1	2	7	
6	6	4	4	1	6	7	6	2	2	6	2	7	6	4	4	2	2	2	6	2	6	2	4	2	6	
6	6	1	1	2	6	7	4	2	1	6	2	7	6	6	7	2	1	1	6	1	7	2	1	2	7	
6	6	2	2	2	6	6	4	2	4	6	2	6	6	4	6	2	2	2	6	2	6	2	2	2	6	
7	7	2	1	1	7	7	6	2	1	7	2	7	7	7	6	2	1	1	6	2	7	1	2	2	6	
7	7	2	2	2	4	6	4	1	1	6	2	6	4	7	7	1	1	2	6	2	7	1	2	4	4	
4	2	6	4	4	2	1	4	4	7	1	4	4	2	6	4	4	6	4	4	6	4	4	4	6	4	
6	7	2	2	1	6	6	2	2	2	6	1	6	6	7	6	2	2	1	6	2	7	2	2	2	6	
6	7	4	2	6	4	6	4	4	4	4	2	4	6	2	4	2	4	4	4	2	4	6	4	4	2	4
6	6	1	2	2	7	6	4	2	2	6	1	6	6	6	7	1	1	2	6	1	7	1	1	1	7	
4	1	7	7	7	1	1	1	7	7	1	6	1	1	1	1	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	7	1	
6	6	2	2	2	6	6	2	2	2	6	2	6	6	6	6	2	2	2	6	2	6	2	2	2	6	
6	6	4	1	2	6	7	4	4	2	6	4	6	6	4	7	4	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	
6	6	2	2	4	4	6	6	1	2	6	2	6	6	4	6	2	2	1	6	2	6	2	4	2	6	
6	6	1	2	2	4	7	6	4	1	6	2	7	4	6	7	2	2	1	4	1	4	4	2	1	6	
7	6	1	1	1	7	7	6	1	2	6	1	7	7	6	7	1	1	2	6	1	6	1	1	1	6	
7	7	1	1	1	7	7	7	2	1	7	1	7	7	1	7	2	1	1	6	2	4	1	1	1	4	
6	4	2	2	2	7	6	2	4	4	6	1	4	7	7	6	1	1	2	7	4	7	2	1	1	7	
6	4	1	4	6	7	7	6	1	2	7	1	6	6	7	6	2	2	2	7	6	6	4	2	1	7	
7	7	1	1	1	7	7	7	1	1	7	7	7	7	7	7	1	1	1	7	1	7	1	1	1	7	

UEQ Analysis Data Result Using 6 Element Aspect

Item	Mean	Variance	Std. Dev.	No.	Left	Right	Scale
1	↑ 1,9	1,4	1,2	30	annoying	enjoyable	Attractiveness
2	↑ 1,7	2,9	1,7	30	not understandable	understandable	Perspiciuity
3	↑ 1,5	3,2	1,8	30	creative	dull	Novelty
4	↑ 1,8	2,1	1,4	30	easy to learn	difficult to learn	Perspiciuity
5	↑ 1,3	3,5	1,9	30	valuable	inferior	Stimulation
6	↑ 1,4	3,2	1,8	30	boring	exciting	Stimulation
7	↑ 1,9	3,5	1,9	30	not interesting	interesting	Stimulation
8	→ 0,8	3,2	1,8	30	unpredictable	predictable	Dependability
9	↑ 1,4	2,7	1,6	30	fast	slow	Efficiency
10	↑ 1,5	3,1	1,8	30	inventive	conventional	Novelty
11	↑ 1,7	2,7	1,6	30	obstructive	supportive	Dependability
12	↑ 1,6	2,4	1,6	30	good	bad	Attractiveness
13	↑ 1,9	1,9	1,4	30	complicated	easy	Perspiciuity
14	↑ 1,5	3,2	1,8	30	unlikable	pleasing	Attractiveness
15	↑ 1,3	3,9	2,0	30	usual	leading edge	Novelty
16	↑ 1,7	2,6	1,6	30	unpleasant	pleasant	Attractiveness
17	↑ 1,9	1,9	1,4	30	secure	not secure	Dependability
18	↑ 1,7	2,8	1,7	30	motivating	demotivating	Stimulation
19	↑ 1,8	2,0	1,4	30	meets expectations	does not meet expectations	Dependability
20	↑ 1,6	2,6	1,6	30	inefficient	efficient	Efficiency
21	↑ 1,5	3,0	1,7	30	clear	confusing	Perspiciuity
22	↑ 1,6	2,9	1,7	30	impractical	practical	Efficiency
23	↑ 1,4	3,1	1,8	30	organized	cluttered	Efficiency
24	↑ 1,6	2,4	1,5	30	attractive	unattractive	Attractiveness
25	↑ 1,9	2,2	1,5	30	friendly	unfriendly	Attractiveness
26	↑ 1,3	3,1	1,8	30	conservative	innovative	Novelty

UEQ Scales (Mean and Variance)		
Attractiveness	↑ 1,717	1,63
Perspiciuity	↑ 1,742	1,89
Efficiency	↑ 1,500	2,22
Dependability	↑ 1,525	1,59
Stimulation	↑ 1,558	2,59
Novelty	↑ 1,408	2,27

Data Result UEQ Scale (Mean & Variance)

Reliability Final Data Using Alpha Cronbach's

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item_1	98.6333	438.792	.816	.976
Item_2	98.7000	433.321	.698	.977
Item_3	98.8333	424.489	.877	.975
Item_4	98.6667	432.851	.805	.976
Item_5	99.0000	427.724	.786	.976
Item_6	98.9000	426.300	.841	.976
Item_7	98.6000	422.524	.846	.976
VAR00035	99.3000	443.666	.466	.978
VAR00036	98.9000	430.300	.799	.976
VAR00037	98.8667	426.189	.828	.976
VAR00038	98.8333	428.902	.827	.976
VAR00039	98.6667	436.644	.809	.976
VAR00040	98.6667	435.471	.768	.976
VAR00041	98.8333	428.282	.791	.976
VAR00042	99.0000	435.862	.559	.978
VAR00043	98.7333	429.375	.828	.976
VAR00044	98.6667	432.575	.846	.976
VAR00045	98.7667	425.909	.897	.975
VAR00046	98.7000	430.976	.868	.976
VAR00047	98.8667	433.706	.753	.976
VAR00048	98.8667	432.671	.727	.976
VAR00049	98.8000	431.752	.745	.976
VAR00050	98.9333	428.340	.810	.976
VAR00051	98.7667	429.013	.851	.976
VAR00052	98.6667	434.575	.760	.976
VAR00053	99.0000	429.862	.785	.976

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	30	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	30	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.977	26

Reliability Statistic Result